

THE DEGREE OF ADAPTATION TO PSYCHOGENIC EFFECTS IN SOCIAL LIFE IN PATIENTS WITH PSYCHOGENIC ASTHMA

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Abstract. A study was conducted of patients with bronchial asthma (AD). Forms of bronchial asthma were considered: psychogenically induced, somatopsychogenic, non-atopic psychogenic. A dynamic phase temporal portrait of life events of patients with bronchial asthma is presented. Patients with a psychogenic form of bronchial asthma have been shown to have less "openness" of their temporal system. The control parameters of the system were found to be retrospective time, positive, and negatively assessed (semantic) retrospective time.

Keywords: psychogenic bronchial asthma; life events; temporal analysis; phase space of the quasi-tractor.

Introduction. This work implies empirical implementation an approach to the analysis of temporal events. The empirical studies carried out are within the framework of the development of the synergistic concept in psychology. It can be seen that in this direction it is possible to obtain facts that have not been determined by statistical methods [2].

Timeliness is seen by us as a time interval. This concept defines the time interval in which the identity of the subject can be determined. According to the rules of anthropological psychology, a person is represented in a spatial-temporal organization by an open, multidimensional system extended to the world [1]. There is a subjective reality reflected in the system, whose multidimensional structure includes time and semantic coordinate (topochronous) [3].

"Semantic" time is described by another non-physical time continuity vector and is therefore not part of it. This type of idea allows one to consider "space" both physically and semantically. The "time" vectors are assumed to lie in an orthogonal hypercosm. The openness of the psychological system (PS) is defined as the volume of the phase space of time vectors. This space has a statistical (stochastic) and chaotic center of the dynamical system. The "topochronous" empirical research strategy is most effective in systematic representations. Another strategy of work should be defined as the implementation of an approach to determining the "openness" of psychological systems [4-7].

In terms of the "openness" of the temporal phase space of life phenomena, we consider the temporal properties of the Past – Present – Future (p – n – b) duration, its events [8].

The solution of this type of problem is associated with the practical need to further develop the clinical and psychological typology of diseases, taking into account the individual

psychological characteristics of patients within the framework of an integral-systemic and highly anthropological approach [9-11].

Such presemantics repeats the modern trend of seeing the somatic locus and the pathogenic symbol of the disease as a holistic developing structure that defines personal meanings in the individual body of a person [12].

The concept of Psychosomatic Medicine also shows this. The idea of the integrity of the human body, the evolutionary approach of Medicine, reflects complex links between social causation, human emotional response, and somatic health and the state of psychosomatic illness (PSZ). Personality identity [13-15] is expressed by the structure in the system of identification with ideas, social situations and material objects; educational systems, the way of life; the language of emotions, symbols, signs, the unique language of interaction with the world at the level of corporeality [16].

One of the things that constantly accompany human diseases is bronchial asthma. The psychoanalytic construction of bronchial asthma is seen as a distorted harmony-a collaboration between the need to receive and give love (breathe and breathe). Breathing difficulties similar to crying from the outside can cause deep psychological damage for a number of reasons – the fear of being alone until the age of 5. Recognition of bronchial asthma is determined by the awareness of the need to "take and give". According to the lingopsychoanalytical interpretation of bronchial asthma [17-20] is the unwillingness to live independently, the fear of sincerity, sincerity, the fear of changes that bring unwanted news. Another construct is the positive diagnosis of psychosomatic disease, derived from the ideas about neurotic diseases presented in Myasishchev's works, which can also be used in the diagnosis of psychosomatic disease [21]. The category "psychogenic" is recognized in the form of psychogeny, which is associated with the personality of the patient, the traumatic situation and the difficulty of independent resolution. A certain correspondence is observed between the dynamics of the patient's condition and the change in the psychotraumatic situation – clinical manifestations in its composition are to some extent associated with the psychotraumatic situation and the experiences of the individual, his strongest and deepest aspirations, representing an affective reaction, pathological fixation of some of his experiences [22-24].

The work presents a cognitive model of psychogenically induced bronchial asthma in accordance with the principles of integrity and self-development. The study is aimed at determining the dynamic patterns of the manifestation of this form of adaptation with the formation of body reactions. Integrity is expressed as a recursive self-organizing system of representation of interactions at the level [25].

In ontogenesis, the dissipative, holistic structure of the patient's biopsychosocial organism undergoes many bifurcations, which balance as a correlation of internal manifestations between attractors-brain states. Then any processes in the body, in this case the processes of operation of this cardiorespiratory system, correspond to these situations. Therefore, psychophysiological processes can be such [26-28].

The purpose of the study: Studying the peculiarities of the level of adaptation to psychogenic influences in social life in patients with psychogenic asthma

Materials and research methods. The study grouped 178 patients with bronchial asthma. Groups represent empirically observed phenomena rather than based on clinical criteria. The qualifications of the forms and their corresponding groups were determined for pathogenetic

reasons: psychogenically induced bronchial asthma-psychogenically induced bronchial asthma; BASP – somatopsychogenic bronchial asthma, banp – non-psychogenic bronchial asthma. The average age of patients did not differ between groups. Non-parametric (U -, t-criteria) and parametric statistical methods (comparison of mean values, Anova dispersion analysis) have been applied.

For the heterogeneous group of patients with bronchial asthma, statistical processing and characterization of the behavior of the vector of temporal events in M-dimensional state space was carried out, including using synergistic approaches [2]. For different groups of bronchial asthma, the size and centers of the quasi-tractors (ka) vector of organism States in M-dimensional space, the distance between the stochastic and chaotic centers of the attractors under study, were determined.

Parameters of the layout of quasi-tractors were set. To do this, the volume of phase-phase quasiattractors for clusters of bronchial asthma forms was calculated, and then, according to the algorithm, with simultaneous analysis of the parameters of quasiattractors, individual components of the temporal system state vector were excluded from the calculation. Subsequently, it was compared what changes, significant or insignificant in the parameters of the attractor after such exceptions. The work used the clinical and biographical method of psychological analysis of life events (FS).

Research results and discussion. Human time is represented by the area of the event. It contains events as value-semantic formations that can remain mandatory, eternal. The meanings in the formation of a person are most clearly manifested in time ($p - n - b$).

They objectify the transpective – the general direction of movement of the "human" system. This temporal system can be considered psychological, given the special role of mental factors in self-organization. The openness of the psychological system of a person is also understood as a temporary, event phenomenon.

Past (retrospective) and future (antisipative) time, its temporal "depth" and articulation indicate the degree of openness of the system.

In the first task, the "openness" of the system was analyzed in a temporary, frequency and cognitive-emotional assessment of the phenomena of retrospection and antisipation.

Within the framework of the second task, the issue of assessing the phase gaps of the temporal structures of the vital phenomena of patients with bronchial asthma was solved.

The first hypothesis showed that the "openness" of the psychological system of patients with bronchial asthma, determined by removal to the past, to the future, as well as cognitive-emotional assessment, is expressed to a lesser extent than in healthy people. according to the second hypothesis, the degree of openness of temporary PS is observed in groups of patients with bronchial asthma, in which the formation of the disease is influenced by psychological factors (group of patients with bronchial asthma with psychogenic effects; bronchial asthma with psychogenic effects).

First task. Empirically determined the time of retrospective and antisipation in patients with bronchial asthma, as well as the regime of retrospective and antisipation phenomena with varying degrees of involvement of anxiety-depressive components in the etiopathogenesis of the disease.

Retrospective time. Anova has shown that the average retrospective time varies according to the form of bronchial asthma in patients ($F = 4.82$; $p = 0.009$). The longest time of retrospective (BP) is typical of patients with bronchial asthma psychogenically induced.

This indicates a specific psychological "blockage" of patients in this group in the past (usually BP is about 2 times shorter). Psychological assessment of retrospective phenomena as emotionally significant has shown that there is no statistical difference between groups of patients with bronchial asthma.

Antisipation time. The average time of antitasking of events (and) varied significantly for patient groups. In the farthest future (years) it manifests in patients with bronchial asthma non-psychogenic (3.02 ± 1.98) and in the least patients with bronchial asthma psychogenically induced (0.51 ± 1.40).

And is a highly informative feature, according to the measurement of the hut, for patients with bronchial asthma with 5.8 times more information compared to psychogenic induced bronchial asthma psychogenically induced.

The greatest future positive assessments are patient-specific bronchial asthma psychogenically induced, while the smallest are patients psychogenically induced bronchial asthma. The negative assessment of future events varied according to the form of bronchial asthma ($F = 3.25$, $p = 0.04$). Patients were given the greatest negative assessment of bronchial asthma psychogenically induced (0.11).

Thus, the hypothesis that the psychological system of people with bronchial asthma is less "open" in the characteristics of the temporal structure compared to the psychogenic form of the disease has been confirmed.

Analysis of events. Another approach supporting the hypothesis suggests a positive or negative difference in frequency of retrospective (MS) and antisipation (As) events assessed by patients with bronchial asthma.

ANOVA shows that the frequency of past events varies in diagnostic groups ($F = 10.93$, $p = 0.00$). The lowest level of past events is typical of patients bronchial asthma not psychogenic. The informative composition of the sign" number of retrospective negative phenomena " is 4.1 times higher for patients bronchial asthma psychogenically induced than for patients with psychogenic induced bronchial asthma.

The frequencies of future events (semantic field of antisipation events) differed between diagnostic groups ($F = 24.28$, $p = 0.00$). The lowest rate of antisipation events occurs in a group of patients with bronchial asthma psychogenically induced.

Events were also classified according to the severity of the personal reaction (weak, moderate, strong) and the type of events (biological, personal-psychological, associated with natural or socio-environmental changes). Assessing the subjective significance of the future showed that the frequencies of "insignificant" and "moderate" phenomena did not differ between groups of patients with bronchial asthma ($F = 1.86$, $p = 0.16$).

The most obvious frequency of future "strong" events for patients is bronchial asthma non-psychogenic (2.73 ± 1.5), bronchial asthma psychogenically induced (1.37 ± 1.56), and bronchial asthma psychogenically induced (0.59 ± 0.91) compared to patients ($F = 45.53$, $p = 0.000$; sheffe method $p < 0.001$).

The frequencies of small and moderately significant events for the past time did not differ statistically. The informative content of the" number of significant retrospective negative phenomena " Hut sign is 2.6 times higher for patients with bronchial asthma psychogenically induced, than in the group of people with aapn.

The assessment of past and future time was dominated by the assessment of events as "significant" bronchial asthma psychogenically induced compared to other forms of bronchial asthma (12.66) (17.54 and 15.37; $F = 10.15$, $p = 0.00$).

The informativeness of the sign (in terms of the hut) "total number of anticipatory negative phenomena" indicates that for patients, psychogenically induced bronchial asthma is not psychogenic, this feature is 6.6 times more informative, that is, it is decisive in differential assessment.

The informative composition of the sign "number of significant anticipatory negative phenomena" is 9.8 times higher for patients bronchial asthma compared to the group of individuals with psychogenically induced BAPN. The temporal phase space of vital phenomena this indicator is also a determining feature in the differential assessment of the temporal-semantic permanence of patients, especially for patients. bronchial asthma is psychogenically induced.

Patients' assessment of the type of event varies depending on the form of bronchial asthma. Differences were found for events identified as biological exposure Type ($F = 3.42$, $p = 0.04$) and natural variation-related species ($F = 6.29$, $p = 0.002$). These categories are listed in [3].

A comparison of typological assessments of events showed that higher values for a group of individuals had psychogenically induced social impact events in bronchial asthma. An important feature is the density of past and future events. Analysis of the density of N events at the elapsed time (n / t) does not indicate the dependence of the indicator values on the form of bronchial asthma ($F_{2;175} = 2.64$, $p = 0.075$).

For the coming time, in contrast, there is a dependence of the density of N/T events on the nosological form of bronchial asthma ($F_{2;134} = 5.92$, $p = 0.003$). N / t future bronchial asthma unlike non – psychogenic forms 1.19 bronchial asthma psychogenically induced – 0.69 ($p = 0.05$) and bronchial asthma psychogenically induced-0.53 ($p = 0.02$) according to the sheffe method.

Patient cluster quasi-tractor randomness bronchial asthma is psychogenically induced ($10e+26$ vs $10e+25$) compared to other groups bronchial asthma, which characterizes an unstable type of Organization of temporal continuity in the cluster. The closest are the chaotic centers of the temporal quasi-tractors of the groups bronchial asthma non-psychogenic and bronchial asthma psychogenically induced.

With a sequential decrease in the size of quasiattractors (removal of parameters and change in the size of quasiattractors), the control parameters of the dynamic system were determined. They are: retrospective time; retrospective time assessed positively and negatively. It is these parameters that reduce the distance between the chaotic centers of FP to the greatest extent.

Discussion. The work identified temporal features of empirically constructed anthroposystems of asthma patients, based on the concept of probabilistic forecasting and anticipation using the biopsychosocial approach used in interdisciplinary research.

Conclusion. Timeliness shows that time is characterized not only by physical, but also by historical, semantic content. This coordinate is important in life space and is included in the psychological subsystem of the anthroposystem. The most important feature of a dynamical system is the openness–proximity property. This reflects the nonlinear nature of the temporal phase space of life events in the dynamics of the self-organizing system. In the temporal "space" of a person, the sign of the openness of the system has the meaning of temporary phenomena in the first place.

In the study, the phenomenon of less "openness" of the system is represented by the longest retrospective time (BP) data typical of patients with psychogenic asthma.

In addition, a phase analysis of the temporal properties of FS has shown that the control parameters of a dynamic self-organizing system are retrospective time, as well as retrospective time, which is assessed positively and negatively. The elapsed time is a kind of "introduction" to the system, but it is also an element of feedback (the most important aspect of the activity of the dynamic system) by the "future". This is close to the idea of transvective analysis, where historical time shows the effect of multivariate futures on the monovariate past. Thus, using the Phase Space method, the properties of FS time were determined, which play an important role in the formation of the current state of anxiety in patients with psychogenic forms of bronchial asthma.

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